

VIVA SAN AGUSTÍN

by

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About the Author

Gabriella Estrada is a fourth-year Cinema and Television Arts major with a focus on writing. She is also minoring in Creative Writing and is working on completing a Spanish Translation Certificate. Gabriella aspires to be a head screenwriter for an original television series, as well as a published poet and author. She has written a variety of short stories, poetry, and screenplays, and has completed her first novella for her senior honors project. *Viva San Agustín* is set in her hometown in Mexico during the 1920s Cristero War. The novel was inspired by stories she was told by her family and based on her own childhood memories. It was written in memory of her grandfather, Jose Esparza Perez.

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VIVA SAN AGUSTÍN
In Memory of Jose Esparza Perez

**“From the rising of the sun to its setting
The name of the Lord is to be praised.”
- Psalm 113:3**

CAPÍTULO 1

The sun always remembered its place among the hills of Tlachichila.

It was just beginning to rise, and its rays were filling the heavens with tinges of orange, white, and purple. The air was crisp and filled with anticipation of the coming day. Everything was still. It had rained the night before, and the red earth was moist and bursting with the promise of what was to come. In the distance, a crowd of roosters began to crow, marking the inevitable start of the day. Soon, the town would come to life, as it did every morning.

As the rays of light stretched themselves onto the clock tower and lightly touched its surface, its bells began to ring over and over again, following the melody that had been ingrained in their cracks and crevices.

When the sun took its rightful place in the sky, the people of Tlachichila began to rise from within their clay homes, ready to take their own rightful places within the town. It was Sunday. Everything was more beautiful on Sundays.

Deep within the town, the stillness was broken by the sound of a gasp. The brightness had stolen Solecito from the depths of her sleep, and she sat up in bed clutching her chest tightly. Her head hit the edge of her bedframe ever so slightly, but she ignored it and instead called into the emptiness before her.

“Jacinto?”

The sound of her voice was barely above a whisper. She pushed a series of red and gray quilts off her trembling body and slid out of bed. With each step, the ground seemed to become farther and farther away from her bare feet.

“Jacinto?” She ran into his bedroom and tore the quilts from his bed. Empty.

Solecito ran to the door, feeling her long braids pounding against her back. She threw the wooden door open and felt the chilly air immediately prickle her skin. Her short exhales became clouds of fog before her mouth, and her feet sunk into the soil beneath her. The silence that greeted her was overbearing, and she clutched her nightgown tightly.

In the distance, two figures began to come closer and closer into view, as two young boys ran swiftly down the dirt road.

“Come on, hurry up!” Fausto called back, running as fast as his legs could carry him.

Jacinto struggled to keep up, weighed down by the crushed bullets that were clinking in his pockets. “I can’t!”

“Your sister’s going to yell at you!” Fausto said in a sing-song voice.

Jacinto scowled and began to run faster, until he reached the barrier of rocks surrounding his house. He stood before it and watched Fausto run past, going at such a speed that it almost seemed as if he were flying. He wiped the smile off his face before walking toward his home, where his sister was waiting for him. His scowl resurfaced.

Solecito released her nightgown and crossed her arms. “Where have you been?”

He sighed exasperatedly. “Nowhere, Solecito.”

Solecito heard the bullets clinking in his pockets and grabbed him roughly by the arm. She resisted his attempts to be released from her grasp and emptied his pockets. The bullets fell to the ground pathetically, and he looked up with guilt in his eyes.

“Jacinto,” she breathed, pressing her hands to her temples. “How many times have I told you—”

“We were being careful!” he whined, stomping his foot on the ground impatiently.

“It’s not safe!” she snapped. Her hands began to shake, and she dragged out her breathing in an attempt to calm herself. “Jacinto, they could *kill* you. It’s not safe. You need to stop going near those *federales*. And you need to stop dragging that boy with you.”

“We’re just collecting them. We’re not doing anything. The *federales* weren’t even there!”

“Just *stop*.” She said it in the most serious and intimidating tone she could muster, and then took a breath. “If I ever catch you coming home with bullets ever again, I’m telling Mamá.”

Jacinto’s eyes filled with fear, and she exhaled in satisfaction. She grabbed him by the shoulder and led him to his room.

“Change your clothes and get rid of the bullets,” she called back. “Mamá is still sleeping but she’ll be awake soon. I don’t want her to know what you were doing.”

“Yes, *María de la Soledad*.”

Solecito turned back. “*Jacinto de María Huerta Macías*.”

“Don’t call me that!” Jacinto complained, running into his room in defeat.

Solecito smiled slightly, and then returned to her room to change into her clothes for the day. As she slid her long skirt into place, she looked exhaustedly at the pile of laundry that was sitting in

a cloth sack in the corner of her room. She pulled her braids into a tight knot at the back of her head, slid on her sandals, and picked up the sack from the ground. Before leaving her house, she grabbed a bag of powdered Roma detergent and wrapped a brown shawl tightly around herself.

The walk to the river would not be far, but Solecito found herself dreading every moment. With each step, the sack seemed to grow heavier and heavier in her already trembling fingers, and the smell of the Roma powder was beginning to make her nose itch uncomfortably. The gravel cracked beneath her leather sandals with each step, and the passing breeze was not enough to disguise the growing heat that was settling in the morning air.

When she arrived at the river, she knelt onto the ground, brushing her skirt beneath her knees so that the pebbles would not pierce her skin. Solecito always dreaded washing clothes. The responsibility of washing her family's clothes was tedious and laborious, but she knew it was hers to bear.

As she covered a skirt in Roma powder and dipped it into the water beneath her to begin scrubbing, she watched the soap suds travel down the river idly. They floated past the other women who had chosen to wash their clothes that morning and continued their steady path until they disappeared.

The skirt weighed heavily in her hands, which were starting to become irritated. Solecito raised it from the water and began to squeeze out the water gently. As she reached to place the skirt beside her, a man appeared on the road and ran toward her. He landed next to her, and she moved away quickly.

“What are you doing?” she asked, her heart beating rapidly in her chest.

When he looked up at her, she noticed that his forehead was beaded with sweat, and he was breathing heavily. There was a look of exhaustion and fear behind his eyes. He bent down to drink from the river, and her heart slowed.

“Don’t do that,” she warned. “I’ve been washing clothes. The water will taste like soap.”

“Oh.” He sat back down on the ground and crossed his legs.

Solecito eyed him carefully. A sense of uneasiness began to crawl through her body. She had known every person who had ever lived in Tlachichila since she was born – every family member, every friend, every foreigner that had chosen to move there. But she had never seen this man before, and it filled her with a sense of discomfort.

“What’s your name?”

He wiped the sweat beads off his forehead with the bottom of his shirt. “Jesús.”

Solecito cocked her head. “Who are your parents?”

“Adela and Dagoberto.”

“From which family?”

The man splashed his face with water and sighed in relief. “You certainly ask a lot of questions.”

“I know everyone here. I’ve never seen you before.”

“That’s because I’m not *from here*.”

“Where are you from, then?”

The young man sighed again and turned to face her. Solecito studied his face closely for the first time. His eyes were deep and dark, his skin was tanned from spending hours and hours outside, and his grown-out hair was plastered to his forehead.

He eyed her slowly. “*Jalpa*.”

Solecito reached for Jacinto's shirt, which was sitting on top of the pile of clothes beside her and pushed it into the river gently. She felt the urge to ask more questions rise in her chest, but she sensed his tension and decided against it.

"I understand that you're uneasy," he began. "But I'm not going to hurt anybody. I just...I want *water*. I'm hungry. I'm tired."

The Roma powder slipped through her fingers. "Oh."

"And I ran away from my family."

He stared off into the distance, and she lowered her head. "I'm sorry."

He reached up to wipe the sweat off his face again. "Does that answer all of your questions?"

Solecito jerked her head, but then realized that there was a smile beginning to form on his face.

"Yes. I'm sorry. I'm just anxious."

"I understand."

She took a moment to squeeze the water out of Jacinto's shirt, and then turned to face him again. He stood from the ground and brushed dirt off his pants.

"Where are you going?" she asked.

"I don't know," he admitted. "To find clean water, I think."

"And then?"

“I’ll figure it out.” he said, nodding his head as if to convince himself that it was true. After a brief pause, he went to speak again. “May I have your name before I go?”

Her heart pounded in her chest painfully, and she exhaled to soothe it. “María de la Soledad Huerta Macías. Solecito.”

“Solecito,” he repeated. “Thank you.”

“Wait,” she called. “Before you leave, would you like to have breakfast with my family? We don’t have much, but we can –”

“You don’t have to do that.”

“Please,” she insisted. “Let me help you. At least let me get you some water.”

He hesitated but nodded in defeat. When Solecito finished washing her clothes, the two carried them in their arms all the way back to her home. They began to use clothespins to hang them on the thin wires that extended from wall to tree outside. He watched as the drops of river water began to pool on the ground, and the grass quickly became moist.

“Come inside,” Solecito said. His gaze broke away from the ground and focused back on her. “I have water and food for you.”

The man followed her into her home and looked around. His eyes passed over the wooden planks beginning to come loose from the ceiling and the walls that were beginning to crumble.

Solecito stepped into the kitchen, and he followed closely behind. She stared deeply into a clay pot sitting on the table. There were hundreds of beans sitting in a broth in the pot, and they appeared to be very charred.

A woman appeared from behind the walls containing the kitchen. She was older, and had large gray streaks mixed in her dark hair. Her body was thin and frail, and she seemed to be holding it together with a thick black shawl.

“Good morning, Soledad.”

“Good morning, Mamá.” Solecito replied. Her eyes did not stray from the pot, and her mother watched her sadly. “This is Jesús. I’ve invited him to have breakfast with us today.”

Mateo stepped forward and extended his hand. “Thank you for welcoming me into your home.”

Her mother smiled politely. Solecito frowned and turned toward the hallway. “Jacinto!”

Jacinto ran into the kitchen, and Solecito pushed the hair out of his face. “Are you hungry?”

Jacinto nodded enthusiastically. “Go wash your hands, please.”

Solecito reached for a clay bowl and filled it with the burned beans. As she sifted through the pot, the man’s nose twitched. The beans had a strong, unpleasant odor, but he knew that they would satisfy his intense hunger regardless. Solecito rested the bowl on his palms, and his fingertips began to tingle from the warmth. She left another bowl on the table for Jacinto, and then turned to him again.

“Come,” she said. “Let’s sit outside.”

He followed behind her, and the two sat on the protruding roots of a large tree.

“Are you not having breakfast?” he asked.

“I am,” she answered. She looked up, and when he followed her gaze, he saw that there were dozens of bright red pomegranates on the branches above them. He gasped. The pomegranates

were beautiful. They were a strong, pure red color, and they reflected the light on their smooth surfaces. “Would you like to try them?”

“Yes, please,” he responded finally. “Thank you. You are too kind.”

“Don’t worry about it.” Solecito rose from the ground and brushed the grass off of her palms. She climbed on top of a nearby root and used the tips of her fingers to grab a large pomegranate that was right above his head. She used her fingernails to try and pry the skin away. “God says that we should help others, and that’s what I’m trying to do now.”

He watched her briefly before extending his hand. “I can do that for you.”

He reached into his pocket and retrieved a small, thin knife, which he then used to slice the pomegranate in half. He placed one of the halves in her palm and began to retrieve the seeds carefully.

They sat in silence for a long moment, enjoying the bittersweet taste of the fruit on their tongues. When he finished his half, he brushed his hands on his pants and stood up. There was a fresh stain of pomegranate juice on his brown pants, and the sight made her smile briefly.

“I should go,” he began. “But I wanted to thank you for all that you have done for me today.”

“It’s the least I can do,” she replied simply.

A smile appeared on his face. “Can I see you again someday?”

“Solecito!” a voice called from the distance. “Mamá can’t find my uniform! Does this mean I can skip school tomorrow?”

Solecito sighed deeply. “I’m sorry, I have to go find his sweater before he gets any ideas. But yes, we can see each other again if you ever need help—”

“Oh, no. That’s not what I meant. I meant see you again...just to see you.”

Solecito blinked. “Oh. Yes. That — yes. That would be all right.”

“Until next time, then.”

“Until next time.”

Solecito watched him leave until his figure was a mere blur, disappearing into the folds of the horizon. She turned back to her house, where Jacinto was waiting for her at their doorstep. A flock of birds flew quickly overhead, and she caught a brief glimpse of their blue feathers. When the birds disappeared, she placed her hand on Jacinto’s shoulder and gently guided him into the house. He placed his fingers on her hand in response.

CAPÍTULO 2

He continued his journey down the road, hoping that he would be suddenly struck with an idea of where to go. The sun was beating down aggressively on his exposed neck, and his breath began to shorten. He reached his palm up to swipe the beads of sweat off his forehead in one quick motion.

“Cruz. Cruz!”

He turned his head briskly, and at the sight of the figure behind him, he began to run at full speed.

“Stop!” the figure called. “*Mateo Cruz*, stop!”

The figure caught up and knocked him to the ground. He groaned in pain, feeling the gravel cut into his elbows.

“What did you do that for? Get off me!”

“Where have you been?”

He rolled over, and his gaze was met by a young man wearing a light brown uniform. The buttons on his jacket were round and gold, and he wore a dark leather belt and boots. His hat was sitting on his head at an awkward angle and seemed to be clinging to his dark hair frantically. His eyes were full of anger and concern.

“It doesn’t matter,” he responded shortly.

“The general doesn’t know where you are.”

Mateo furrowed his brow. “What?”

“I didn’t tell him. I wanted to look for you myself. Come back with me, please. Don’t make this harder than it needs to be. He’ll end you if he finds out. He’ll end *us*.”

Mateo turned his head sharply. “No. Go back and tell him you couldn’t find me.”

“Are you *crazy*? You—”

“I ran away. Yes, I know what I did. I don’t need you to tell me.”

“Cruz,” he breathed. “Mateo. *Please*. Just come back. It’s not too late.”

Mateo looked off into the distance. A long silence passed between them.

Finally, when their eyes met again, he said, “Forgive me, Tomás.”

Tomás’s expression hardened. “Where will you go? Where will you go if you don’t come back with me?” Mateo’s jaw clenched, and Tomás continued. “Don’t forget yourself. We would have nothing if it wasn’t for General Gutiérrez.”

“I know.”

“Then come back with me.”

Every ounce of Mateo’s being wanted to protest. He wanted to argue. He wanted to change. He wanted to face his fears and keep running; he wanted to start a new life that did not involve war, sacrifice, exhaustion, confusion, loneliness. But when he looked into the face of Tomás, his lifelong friend, the man who had stood by his side for years, he found himself unable to say no. Tomás exhaled victoriously. He stood from the ground and offered his hand to Mateo. The two brushed the dirt off their clothes and began to walk.

“Mateo,” Tomás began cautiously. “Where have you been?”

“I ran off into a town and found a girl. She fed me and gave me water,” Mateo answered vaguely.

“A *Cristero*?”

“No. I don’t know. It doesn’t matter.”

“Oh, no, don’t tell me she *converted* you.”

“You should be grateful that she saved my life instead of focusing on whether or not she tried to introduce me to God, Tomás.”

“Did you tell her who you are?”

“No, of course not. I didn’t even tell her my real name. I’m not an *idiot*.”

“Right, whatever. If you say so.” Tomás paused, and his tone softened. “I’m just glad you’re back.”

Mateo put his hands in his pockets and exhaled loudly. He glanced over his shoulder briefly and wondered if he would ever be able to return to the river and see Solecito again. But Tomás’s question of whether she had been a *Cristero* came back to his mind, and his stomach twisted into knots.

Mateo thought about their interaction again. He thought about the soap suds flowing in the river, the sun beating down on their backs, the smell of charred beans, the beads of pomegranate juice running down their palms, her hesitant smile, and her devotion to God. Although he felt an aching in his chest, he decided that he would try to forget his moment of weakness and follow Tomás instead.

As he followed closely behind, he could almost hear the echo of church bells beginning to ring. He closed his eyes gently, as though it would keep the sound out. As he kept walking forward, it almost seemed to work. The echoes died in response.

CAPÍTULO 3

“Jacinto!” Solecito yelled. “Jacinto, your uniform is under the bed. Stop trying to hide it from me!”

“No!” Jacinto ran past her, and Solecito ran after him frustratedly.

“Jacinto!”

“No, no! I don’t want to go to school! It’s not fair! *You* don’t have to go.”

Solecito caught up to him and pulled him by the shoulders. She turned him to face her and knelt to be at eye level.

“Jacinto,” she said calmly. “I want you to have a better life than me.”

“But why do I have to go to school if you don’t?”

Solecito’s heart sank. She brushed the hair out of his face gently. “I can’t go to school because I have to take care of you and help Mamá.”

“I don’t want to go to school anymore.”

“I know,” she said. “I know. But can you try for me? Please?”

“I can try,” he said, nodding reluctantly.

Solecito embraced him. As she held him close to her, she realized how small he felt in her arms, and she pulled him in tighter.

“Do you want some fruit from the market?” she asked finally.

He nodded enthusiastically, and they walked to the market together holding hands.

The vendors had already arrived at the market by then, and they had covered their shops from the rays of the sun. They had taken their places on the uphill street with the misshapen, cracked concrete, and had laid their products on plastic mats and tables. Copper colored pots and pans, artisanal figurines, household necessities, and children's toys filled the stands. They sat quietly across from the rice, beans, vegetables, and freshly cut fruit that were awaiting the eager hands and mouths that would come running.

Solecito and Jacinto looked at the stands joyfully. The streets were filled with children running around excitedly, parents jogging closely behind, and couples walking side by side.

Jacinto ran toward the fruit stand and beamed at the woman before him. Milagritos sold cut fruit every Sunday, and she sprinkled salt, lemon, and spices onto it. On weekdays, she sold street corn, both in cups and whole, and she had grown to be an important part of the town.

Jacinto's eyes glimmered excitedly as he eyed the fresh pineapple, watermelon, cucumber, honeydew melon, mango, jicama, and oranges that were sitting on the stand before him. A swarm of bees were dancing around the fruit rapidly, and he eyed them with a grin on his face. Jacinto asked Milagritos to begin preparing his fruit cup. As he stood distracted, Solecito felt a tap on her shoulder. She turned around swiftly.

“Señor Cura Emmanuel!” she exclaimed.

He smiled warmly. “Good afternoon! Have you brought your brother to enjoy the market?”

She grinned. “He wants to come every Sunday. Sundays are his favorite day of the week. I don't know what to do with him sometimes. He throws a tantrum if he doesn't get his cup of fruit.”

The priest chuckled softly. “Well, I'm glad to see that at least one person is having a good time.”

Solecito's smile faltered. "What do you mean?"

His voice dropped to a whisper, out of earshot from everyone around them. "It's the *federales*, Soledad. They've been to *Jalpa*."

Solecito's heart began to pound aggressively. "They have?"

"Yes."

Her mouth was dry. "When?"

"Late last night."

"Oh. How did you...find out?"

"Everybody knows, Soledad. Information has been traveling quickly lately. People want to keep each other informed. They want to protect each other."

Solecito wrapped her arms around herself. "I see."

"I have to travel to Las Amarillas for confessions next week. I'm concerned about what may happen there. They might be waiting for me." He stopped to rub his temples. "Soledad, they've already tried to eradicate public worship. I'm worried this will continue. I'm worried that people will stop wanting to come to church. And I can't really blame them, either. We don't know if or when they'll come here."

Solecito swallowed weakly. "I... I'm sure they won't. Not here. Not in our Tlachis."

"Do you understand the kinds of risks we're taking by even continuing to have mass? To have *peregrinaciones*? To even pray together? Do you know what could happen if we were caught?"

“I know...I know.”

His expression darkened. “One of the men there...in Jalpa...he began to shout ‘*Viva Cristo Rey*’ in support of the *Cristeros*. He was shot dead, Soledad. The *federales* have no mercy.”

Solecito looked toward Jacinto, who was running back toward her with an overflowing cup of fruit. Milagritos was laughing and waving behind him. Solecito waved back half-heartedly.

“Good afternoon, Señor Cura!” Jacinto shouted, with his mouth full of watermelon. Red juices were pouring down his chin, and Solecito reached to wipe them off of his face with her thumb.

“Good afternoon!” he responded, forcing a jovial look upon his face. He turned back to Solecito briefly. “May God be with us all.”

He turned to walk away, and Solecito pulled Jacinto closer to her.

“Jacinto,” she breathed. “We’re going to church tonight.”

Jacinto shoved a large piece of watermelon into his mouth whole. “Why?”

“Because it’s what God wants,” she replied hastily.

“If you say so,” he shrugged.

As soon as the sun set that night, Solecito, Jacinto, and their mother set off to church. As they grew closer to the building, the clock tower’s call became more and more powerful, beckoning everyone to enter. Jacinto spotted Fausto and his family, and he yelled Fausto’s name to wave.

The people of Tlachichila walked up the checkered cement stairs together silently. With each passing day, fewer people were brave enough to attend church.

Each step brought them closer to the polished wooden doors of the church, which were bound by dark iron hinges. The church itself was composed of alternating light and dark bricks and was topped by a double arch with two bronze bells. It was complemented by a large white clock tower, which contained a bell in its interior and was topped by a silver cross.

As they stepped inside, they were greeted by the strong smell of roses. The image of the Virgin of Guadalupe was surrounded by piles and piles of flowers from all the people that had visited her that week. The pews in the building were made from dark colored wood, and they were polished and smooth. They were separated by large columns that were covered with sacred images and prayers.

At the very center, behind the altar, San Agustín stood on a pedestal holding a golden staff. The patron saint always stood strong in the center of the church, looking over his people. His porcelain skin was shining, and he was decorated with his black and white garments. He was covered with a red and green robe with gold trimmings, and his right hand was raised as if to bless those who were before him. He seemed to look at each person individually as they filed in, and his expression seemed to glow.

Before he became a saint, San Agustín had been a cruel, sinful man who had lost himself in a life full of vices. As the story goes, his mother spent years praying for her son to turn away from temptation and become a saint. Her prayers were answered when San Agustín began to hear the voice of God. Centuries later, a pair of *arrieros* delivered a statue of San Agustín to the plaza at the very center of Tlachichila, and they mysteriously disappeared. When the statue was discovered, the people made San Agustín their patron saint.

Shortly after the people took their seats, Señor Cura Emmanuel walked in, and the choir began to sing. The church was filled with music from the guitarists and faithful singers. For a moment, despite all the dangers that awaited them, it seemed as though all was well.

The mass was quieter than it usually was. Everyone chimed in for the prayers and responses, but the fear began to settle in very soon after. When the homily was delivered, Señor Cura Emmanuel became silent. After a long pause, he stepped closer to the pews and sighed. “I’m sure that we have all heard the news about Jalpa by now.” The crowd began to fill with uneasy whispers. He cleared his throat before continuing. “Last night, *federales* were seen in Jalpa. They struck down a man for supporting the Cristeros. May he rest in peace. We have offered this mass in his honor.”

The whispers grew louder and louder until the crowd was in complete chaos.

“Viva Cristo Rey!”

The voices stopped. Everyone looked around in horror.

“Who said that?” the priest asked nervously.

Everyone looked around, shooting accusatory glances left and right, but no one claimed the statement.

Señor Cura Emmanuel exhaled deeply. “Let’s pray. May San Agustín protect us from what is coming.”

Solecito looked around the church slowly, analyzing every face in every row carefully, wondering which of them might have proclaimed their support for the Cristeros. No one met her eyes. She looked back down at the ground and joined in the group prayer.

When the prayer concluded, the church became silent in response.

CAPÍTULO 4

“Wait here,” Tomás advised. “I can bring you your jacket and a fresh pair of pants. That way, no one will suspect anything.”

Mateo nodded, and Tomás set off to retrieve the uniform for him. Mateo eyed his surroundings. The federal troops had set up camp in Huanusco, which was just outside of Jalpa.

Tomás and Mateo had only walked a short distance before finding Tomás’s horse and traveling back on it. The thought haunted Mateo. Perhaps their next conquest would force him to see the girl he had met again. Mateo shook his head violently to rid himself of the thought.

“What are you doing?” Tomás called, clicking his tongue in disgust.

“Nothing.”

Tomás eyed him suspiciously. “Right. I brought your uniform.”

“Right. Thank you.”

Mateo hid behind a neighboring tree and began to change into his uniform. He used his old shirt to wipe his face and neck, and as it passed over his left shoulder, he noticed a red stain on it. Pomegranate. Mateo inhaled sharply, and the shirt fell out of his hands and onto the ground.

“What is going on with you? Did that girl poison you?” Tomás asked, raising an eyebrow with an air of concern.

“I’m fine.”

“Well, whatever it is, fix it. You’re going to have to create the perfect lie if you want to fool everyone.”

Mateo and Tomás entered the camp, where all the troops were sitting around a fire.

“Cruz! Fernández! Where have you been?” one man called.

Mateo turned to look at him. The man in question was Sebastián Delgado. He was not, by any means, as dim-witted as Mateo was hoping whoever interrogated him would be, but he knew he could be easily shut down.

“Out and about,” Mateo said.

“You were gone for quite a while,” Sebastián insisted.

“We were doing something for the general.” Tomás snapped.

“Doing what?”

“Why don’t you ask him yourself if you want to know that badly? I can let him know you want to speak with him directly,” Mateo suggested. Sebastián’s smile faded.

“If anyone else has any stupid questions, you can take it up with the general.” Tomás spat. The men remained silent, and Mateo and Tomás went to take a seat next to them.

There was a roar of laughter on the other side of the group, and they turned their attention to the sound.

“Did you see his face when he was chanting that stupid phrase?”

“When he kept saying—”

“‘Long Live Christ the King!’ As if that were enough to save him! Where is your God, now?”

There was another wave of laughter, and Mateo pretended to join. The conversation was interrupted by a booming voice, which made the men rise and stand as straight as they possibly could. General Santiago Gutiérrez stood before them in all of his might, and Mateo found himself wanting to avoid eye contact.

“At ease,” Gutiérrez called. The men relaxed their shoulders, but they continued to stand. “Curfew is at 10 tonight. I need you all to be alert for tomorrow. Tomorrow, we take Huanusco.”

The men roared excitedly in response. Mateo joined them, but the light in his eyes faded. He was reminded, suddenly, of the reason he had tried to leave, and he fought hard to push the thought away as quickly as it had come.

“Mateo,” Tomás called. “You heard the general. Come on, let’s go.”

Mateo followed closely behind him, and the two entered their tents to sleep for the night. He rolled over onto his back and exhaled deeply. As the air escaped from between his lips, it took the form of a wispy, silver-white cloud of smoke.

Mateo sat up to open his tent and looked up. He stared intently at the sky. It was filled with millions of stars, blinking at him and burning through his retinas as though they were exploding suns instead, growing closer and closer to the earth. He thought briefly of Tlachichila, of its rivers and hills and red soil. He thought of the people living inside, and he thought of Solecito and her family sleeping in their home. The memory of her smile and of Jacinto’s laugh made his stomach lurch. He pressed his palms on his abdomen to soothe his discomfort and exhaled deeply again.

Through his breathing, he managed to whisper, “Solecito, I hope we stay away from you.”

To his left, he heard someone shifting in their sleep. Mateo held his breath. He began to hear snoring and sighed in relief.

“Solecito, I hope your God watches over you. I hope he’s real and he protects you from us.”

The night wind howled in response.

“I hope I never see you again.”

CAPÍTULO 5

“Twenty-five divided by five is?”

“Five!”

“Thirty-two divided by eight is?”

“Four!”

“Fifty divided by ten is?”

“Five!”

“*Fausto*,” Jacinto whispered. Fausto continued to answer with the class, and Jacinto frowned.

“*Fausto!*”

Fausto looked over. “*What?*”

Jacinto eyed the teacher carefully. “Let’s leave.”

Fausto raised an eyebrow. “You want to risk it?”

“We can do it.”

The pair waited until the teacher turned around to write on the chalkboard, and then proceeded to sneak out the back door of the classroom. They ran down the hallway until they reached the gardens outside and sat down beneath the shade of a large tree nearby. Jacinto pulled out a bag of marbles from his right pocket. He began to set them down on the grass in neat rows between them.

“I’m going to tell the teacher that you’re skipping class.” a voice called.

Fausto frowned. “Why do you care?”

Jacinto turned his head to find the source of the voice, and found himself looking at a young, skinny boy that was almost a head shorter than himself.

“Go away, Elías.” he demanded.

“No. I’m telling.” Elías said. He turned to run in the direction of the classroom, but Jacinto ran faster than him and grabbed him by the back of the shirt.

“You can’t tell on us if you’re skipping class, too.” he said.

Elías looked back at him. “I’ve skipped class once. You skip class every day. Who do you think is going to win?”

“If you tell the teacher, I’ll tell your mom.”

“At least *my* mom would care,” Elías sneered.

Jacinto released his grip on Elías’s shirt and slammed him into the ground. Elías cried out in pain, and Fausto eyed Jacinto warily.

“Jacinto—”

“Go back to class. I don’t want you to get in trouble. I’m leaving.”

“Jacinto!”

He ran past the school gates and did not turn back. He sped down the road outside, carefully leaped through the stones embedded in the ground, and then jumped onto the sidewalk and ran downhill until he reached the end of the street.

Fausto looked down at Elías with an expression of disgust. “This is your fault.”

He turned and ran back toward the classroom, leaving Elías on the ground in pain. Almost immediately after he returned to class, the students were dismissed for their lunch breaks. They all ran outside toward the school gates, looking for their parents who had brought them lunch. Fausto scanned the crowd urgently, looking for Solecito amongst all of the adults.

“Solecito!” he called, running toward her.

“Hello, Fausto,” she replied. “Where’s Jacinto?”

“He...” Fausto paused and licked his lips anxiously. “He left.”

“What do you mean *he left*?”

Fausto looked down at the ground. “He got in a fight.”

Solecito’s eyes widened, and she covered her mouth with her hand. “Who did he fight? What did he do? Where has he gone?”

“I... I don’t...” he trailed off.

Solecito pulled at her braid roughly behind her back. “Fausto, has your family brought your lunch?”

He looked away shamefully. “No.”

“You can have his.” She placed the lunch in his hands and wiped her sweating palms on her dress. “I’m going to go look for him.”

She turned and began to walk away from the school gates swiftly.

“Wait,” Fausto called. Solecito turned to face him. “Go to the church. He goes there a lot...when he leaves school.”

Solecito felt her stomach twist. She wanted to ask more questions, but she decided that looking for Jacinto was more important. She sped down the street toward the church, hoping that he would still be there when she arrived.

When she entered the church, she found him in front of the altar, kneeling before San Agustín.

She touched his shoulder gently. “Jacinto.”

He faced her slowly. His eyes were red from crying. “Please don’t make me go back.”

Solecito knelt beside him. “I won’t. I just want you to come home.”

Jacinto looked back at San Agustín. “I will. When I’m done praying.”

She nodded in agreement, and the two sat in silence together and prayed. At the end of their prayer, she opened her mouth and said, “Can I ask what happened?”

He looked down at his hands. “He said — well, he kind of said Mamá doesn’t care about me.”

“Oh.” Solecito pressed her fingers down on her palms. “You know that that’s not true, right?”

“I don’t know.” he shifted uncomfortably. “It’s not, right?”

“No. She cares about you very much.”

“Alright,” he replied quietly. “Solecito...you’re my Mamá.”

“Don’t say that.” she chided. She pushed his hair out of his face. “It’s not true. Come on, let’s go home. You can help me clean up around the house.”

He wrinkled his nose in response. When they stood up, he took her hand, and they walked out of the church in silence.

“Jacinto.” Solecito said finally. “Will you go to the *peregrinación* with me this evening?”

“Yes, Solecito.”

She squeezed his hand. “Thank you.”

Jacinto released her hand and began to jump down the stairs.

Solecito turned her gaze up to the sky. The clouds above her head floated past carelessly. They were so thick that they almost looked like scoops of ice cream, melting together and dissolving into the blue sky.

“*Dios mío*,” she whispered. “Deliver us.”

The leaves on the nearby trees rustled restlessly in response, and a loud silence followed.

CAPÍTULO 6

The men were riding down the road on their horses, and Mateo felt nausea begin to crawl up his throat. He was not sure if it was from motion sickness or from nerves, but he felt as though he were about to burst any second.

“Do you know if we’re there yet?” he asked, looking at Tomás hopefully.

Tomás smirked. “We’re almost there.”

“Where are we going?”

“San Juan de los Lagos.”

Mateo nodded silently in response and looked around desperately for any indication that they had entered the town.

“I heard there are going to be a lot of them,” Tomás continued gleefully.

“Why is that?” Mateo questioned.

“The general says they’re having some kind of religious thing at the church,” he answered.

Mateo thought briefly of Tlachichila and blinked hard. “Right. Good for us.”

Suddenly, the group came to a stop. Mateo pulled the reins on his horse and frowned.

“Leave your horses here! We must catch them by surprise,” the General called. The men jumped down from their horses and tied them to the nearby trees, hidden from sight. They began to walk in the direction of the church in San Juan de los Lagos.

“Look,” Tomás whispered excitedly. “Do you see them?”

Mateo peered through the gaps in the trees and saw two crowds of people beginning to meld together. A band was playing music loudly, and the church bells were ringing at an equal volume.

“I see them,” Mateo murmured.

He looked at the crowd closely and it made him feel sick. The crowd was comprised of children, parents, friends, and priests; there were even two pregnant women holding their stomachs happily. He watched them walking toward the church, one by one, ready to sing about their faith to the heavens. From the corner of his vision, he noticed a little boy running around, being chased by an older girl that was trying to get him to behave. He tried to look away at first, but the boy’s giggles caught his attention. His breath caught in his throat.

“*Jacinto.*”

Tomás looked over his shoulder. “What?”

“I said I have to go,” Mateo lied.

“Go where? We’re about to march in!”

“I have to...you know.”

“Just hold it. This is important.”

“I really can’t,” Mateo insisted. “I’ll be back.”

Without waiting for a response, he raced into the nearby trees, and kept running until he was sure he was out of sight. He ran around to the other side of the church, across from where he was

standing. As soon as he was close enough, he threw his jacket into a nearby bush out of sight. He knew he would not have to run into the clearing; he would simply have to make sure he was heard.

“*Jacinto.*” he whispered. The sounds of the music and the crowd overpowered his voice.

“Jacinto!”

Jacinto looked over in his direction suddenly, as if he had heard, but to no avail. Jacinto looked back just as quickly.

“Jacinto!” he called again, as loudly as he could without anyone noticing. Jacinto stepped closer, and they locked eyes finally. “Come here.”

Jacinto raised an eyebrow and tiptoed slowly toward him. “What are you doing here?”

“I’m here you see you.”

“Why?” He looked over his shoulder suspiciously.

“Because I need you to do something for me. I need you to get Solecito and bring her to me. We’re all going to go somewhere together. Can you do that for me?”

Jacinto frowned. “But we’re about to walk back to Tlachichila with everyone.”

“We can go there, too,” Mateo insisted. “But we need to go, now.”

“Why?”

“Please, Jacinto.” Mateo begged. He looked around nervously. “I need you to trust me. Go get her, please.”

“Alright. I’ll go.”

Mateo exhaled in relief. Jacinto ran into the crowd and grabbed Solecito’s hand. She protested at first but followed him to where Mateo was hiding.

“Jesús?” she said, raising an eyebrow. “What are you doing here?”

“I need you to come with me.”

“Why?” she asked. Her breathing accelerated slightly.

“Please. I’ll explain when we’re gone. *Please.*”

“I don’t see why you can’t tell me now.”

Their conversation was interrupted by the sounds of gunshots and screaming. People began to run in every direction, and in the distance, she saw several bodies begin to fall to the ground. Mateo took both of their hands and began to run as fast as he could. He could hear Solecito crying, but he forced himself to continue. He only stopped when they could no longer hear the struggle occurring at the church. He released their hands and began to rub his chest. It was hurting terribly, and he could almost taste blood at the back of his throat. When he looked over to his companions, he saw that Jacinto had fallen to the ground in exhaustion, and Solecito was crying and holding herself tightly.

“Solecito,” he said. “I’m sorry.”

“We left them,” she began, her voice trembling. “We left them to *die.*”

“Most of them will survive,” he said. His voice threatened to crack. “They’re...they just want to prove a point.”

She covered her mouth to stifle the sound of her crying, and he reached for her arm, gently. She reached to embrace him, and they held each other for a long moment. When they released each other, Solecito looked off into the distance, where the soldiers were still fighting against the people of San Juan de los Lagos. In their brown uniforms, they were almost impossible to distinguish from one another at times, and the thought of belonging to their uniformity made Mateo shiver.

Solecito's expression fell suddenly, and she pulled Jacinto close to her. She took a step back, and then two. "Jesús."

Mateo's gaze did not leave the soldiers. "Yes?"

Solecito looked at the soldiers again, and then back at him. Her eyes were staring intently at the color of his pants. "How did you know that we needed to run?"

"I saw them coming before they started attacking everyone. I saw Jacinto and I asked him to go get you so that I could save you."

When he looked into her eyes, she looked as though she wanted nothing more than to believe him, but her trust was beginning to waver.

"When I met you, you told me you ran away from your family," she whispered hoarsely.

"I did. I did run away from my family." Mateo insisted. His voice was beginning to fill with desperation.

"You said..." Solecito began, taking more steps back. "You said you had come from..."

"I lied." he said hastily. "I lied, I'm sorry. My name isn't Jesús. My name is Mateo Cruz. Please, come with me. I can protect you. I can keep you safe. I know what they want. I —"

“No,” she whispered. “No. It can’t be.” He reached for her arm again, but this time she pulled away, turning Jacinto’s face away from him.

“Solecito, please. Let me explain,” he begged.

“You’re one of them.”

“You don’t understand.” Mateo insisted.

“Say it.”

He paused. “What?”

“Say it. Say you’re one of them. I know it’s the truth,” Solecito demanded. Mateo took a step forward, and a tear ran down her cheek. “Get away from me. You’re a killer. Just like the rest of them. I *trusted* you. I *brought you into my home*. I should’ve known. We’re leaving.”

“Wait!” He ran after them and reached to grab her shoulder. “I’m not like them, I promise. I just —”

“Don’t touch me!” she screamed, so loudly that they could almost hear it echo into the heavens. She ripped his hand off her shoulder, and he stepped back. “Stay away from us. I never want to see you again.”

Mateo’s eyes moved to Jacinto, who was staring back at him fearfully. Solecito pulled his arm, and the two began to walk away hurriedly. He watched her until she vanished. She did not turn back in response.

CAPÍTULO 7

The sound of gunshots. Bodies falling to the ground. The sky was bright red, just like their blood, which was beginning to pool on the ground. The church bells were ringing hauntingly. She could hear someone screaming, and the screams were beginning to blend in with the echoes coming from the bell tower. She clawed at her throat in pain. She was the one screaming. Somewhere behind her, a single word was being repeated over, and over, and over again.

Killer. Killer. Killer. Killer.

When Solecito awoke, she was screaming out loud. She sat up in bed quickly and ripped off her covers. The room was dark. She lifted her gaze to the crucifix that was hanging on the top of the wall before her, and she started to sob uncontrollably. She searched blindly for her rosary, which she had left sitting on the top of her bedside table, and she began to pray through her crying. There was a knock on her door, and the door opened slowly.

“Why are you crying?” her mother asked. Her eyes were still half shut from sleeping.

“I’m sorry I woke you, Mamá.” Solecito responded. She reached to wipe the tears from her face and exhaled heavily.

Her mother stepped closer. “Why are you crying, Solecito?”

“I...” she paused for a second, deciding whether or not to continue. “I had a bad dream.”

“What was it about?” her mother asked, carefully.

Solecito shook her head. “Nothing. But Mamá... I brought a soldier into our home. And I saw him again.”

Her mother's eyes widened, but then quickly returned to their normal state as she attempted to mask her shock. She shifted her weight from foot to foot. "Was it at San Juan de los Lagos?"

"Yes. They came and... he saved us. But I didn't know he was a soldier, I swear! I never would've brought him if I..." She sniffed and squeezed her eyes shut.

"He saved you?" her mother asked, raising an eyebrow.

"He snuck away to warn Jacinto and me before the soldiers started...started shooting. He got us to safety and tried to defend himself. I told him I never want to see him again."

"He saved you," her mother repeated. "He saved your lives."

"What does it even matter, anyway?" Solecito rose from her bed angrily. "What does it matter if he spared us? He has killed hundreds. He has no mercy."

"He showed you mercy."

"Why are you defending him, Mamá?" she asked frustratedly. Her blood was beginning to pound painfully in her head.

"I'm not," she said calmly. "I know what he has done. But I also know that God wants us to be forgiving. And I know that we must be grateful for the mercy that he has shown you. He could've left you to die with the rest of them, but he didn't."

"Because he felt guilty."

"Because God showed him the right thing to do."

"What if God doesn't do anything?" Solecito asked. The silence after she spoke hung heavily in the air. "What if... what if things happen simply because they do?"

Solecito did not receive a response, and she continued with fear in her voice. “Mamá, what if the soldiers are right, and God really won’t help us?”

Her mother sat Solecito down gently on her bed. She sat beside her and placed one hand on her knee hesitantly. Solecito flinched ever so slightly at the motion.

“I’m sorry I have not been the mother you needed.”

“You have been.” Solecito responded. The two sat in silence, and Solecito hoped that her mother would believe it. “But Jacinto... Jacinto needs you. He needs your care and attention. He feels unloved.”

“He doesn’t need me,” her mother said blankly. “He has you. You’ve been a better mother to him than I ever could have been.”

But that’s not fair, she wanted to say. I shouldn’t have been forced to grow up and mother him.

Instead, all she said was, “It’s not too late. Don’t let him be an orphan, Mamá.”

“He won’t be.” Her breath trembled. “Can I give you a hug, Solecito?”

“Yes.”

They turned to face each other, and Solecito felt her mother embrace her. It was not necessarily a warm feeling; in fact, Solecito found herself wanting it to be over. The physical touch had made her uncomfortable, but she knew her mother needed her.

When they released each other, her mother exited the room in silence, and Solecito slid back under her covers. The crickets outside her window had stopped singing into the night and had been replaced by birds. They could sense that a new day was about to begin, and they had

already started chirping excitedly to prepare for it, as though their calls would pull the morning sun above the horizon. Solecito brought her quilts closer to her, shut her eyes, and began to pray silently. She went through every prayer she had ever learned in her life until her whispers became slurred, and her eyes shut again.

As she drifted off into sleep, she hoped silently that she had a guardian angel looking out for her somewhere. A bird flapped its wings outside her window in response.

CAPÍTULO 8

“Cruz!” Sebastián called. “Where were you during the fight? I didn’t see you.”

“It was hardly a fight,” Mateo said disdainfully.

Sebastián threw his head back and laughed. “Very true!”

He reached to take another swig of his drink, and Mateo sighed in relief.

“Where were you?” Tomás asked through gritted teeth.

“I told you already.” he said flatly.

“I refuse to believe your business would have taken that long.”

“I was behind you.” Mateo spat. “Now stop questioning me.”

Tomás locked his jaw. He wanted to continue his interrogation, but he knew Mateo would not cooperate. He eyed Mateo’s jacket and raised an eyebrow.

“Why is your jacket so clean, even after that fight?”

Mateo’s heart dropped. “I just cleaned it. Don’t be stupid.”

Tomás seemed to take it as an acceptable answer, and he took a sip of his drink. Mateo sighed in relief and thought about Solecito. He thought about the way she had screamed at him, pushed his hand off of her, and told him she never wanted to see him again. Her words rang in his head repeatedly.

You’re a killer. You’re a killer. You’re a killer.

He took a large sip from his cup, which burned the back of his throat. All around them, the men were drinking tequila in celebration of their successful moves in San Juan de los Lagos. They had successfully shut down the church, destroyed its contents, and shot those who had tried to protest.

“Can I just ask,” Tomás began pointedly. “In the interest of our *friendship*, what’s been going on with you lately?”

Mateo’s gaze fell. “I don’t know what you mean.”

The men roared triumphantly at something someone had said, and Tomás readjusted himself. “Well first I caught you... *you know*. And now it seems like you don’t want to talk about anything. You’re always running off, and you always look uneasy... what’s wrong with you?”

“I’ve been thinking about my family recently,” he lied. “And I think I’m just... having a rough time.”

Tomás nodded understandingly. “Well, you have us now.”

“You’re right.”

“Gutiérrez saved us all,” Tomás said, with a hint of adoration in his voice. “He saved us from being alone, and now we get to make sure everyone else in México is united.”

“You’re right.” Mateo repeated hesitantly.

“That’s why I love what we do,” Tomás continued, finishing the rest of his tequila. “They may not see it now, but once religion is no longer keeping us apart, they’ll be thanking us.”

Tomás rose from the ground and went to grab more tequila. Mateo watched him carefully.

“Tomás, do you ever think about your family?”

“All the time,” he shrugged. “Everyone here is my family.”

“No, I mean... your blood family.”

Tomás blinked. “No. Never. I have everything I need here.”

He left to get another drink, and Mateo was left staring into the bottom of his empty cup.

After refilling his cup with tequila, Tomás stopped to talk to some of the other soldiers. Mateo rose from the ground and watched him solemnly.

“Hey.”

Mateo looked over and saw that Sebastián had been leaning beside him.

“Oh. Hey.” he responded shortly.

“Great day today, right?”

“Very.”

“Fernández was excellent. He stopped one of those Cristeros from attacking the general. It was admirable.”

Mateo’s stomach twisted into knots. “I’m sure it was.”

Sebastián paused and licked his lips in thought. “You and Fernández are close, right?”

Mateo shifted uncomfortably. “You could say that.”

“I would’ve thought you would’ve been right by his side when he went in for the kill.”

“You can’t have it all, I guess.”

“What were you doing during that time?”

He locked his jaw. “I don’t know. What were *you* doing?”

“I think you’re misunderstanding me.”

Mateo’s breath caught in his throat. “If you have something to say to me, then I’d appreciate it if you stopped playing games.” He said it firmly, but his confidence was starting to waver.

“I *saw* you, Cruz.”

Mateo’s cup fell and spilled on the ground. He knelt quickly to pick it up.

“You take me for a fool,” he continued. “But I saw you. I saw you with that girl and her son. I saw you help them get away.”

“He’s not her son,” Mateo croaked. His mouth was becoming increasingly dry. “And I didn’t help them do anything. I offered a warning and left.”

Sebastián laughed and took a large swig of his drink. “Now, Cruz, what would you do if I were to tell the general about this?”

“Kill you.” Mateo spat. But even as he said it, he knew he would never be able to do it.

Sebastián laughed again, this time with more vigor. “Oh, you don’t have it in you. You’ve never had it in you. You’ve always been *soft*. I have no idea why Gutiérrez hasn’t killed you already.” He leaned in close and pressed himself against Mateo’s ear. “I wish he would.”

“Then do it yourself.” He retorted. His hands were shaking violently, and he pressed them against his legs to stop the tremors.

“No. Watching you suffer is a far greater pleasure.” Sebastián began to walk away. “Besides, why should I rid myself of the joy of watching *Tomás* be the one to end you when he finds out what you’ve been doing?”

With one final smirk, Sebastián turned and walked away, leaving Mateo trembling with drops of tequila running down his hands.

“What were you doing with Delgado?” Tomás asked with a new drink sitting in his hand.

“How much did you hear?” Mateo asked.

“None of it.” Tomás downed half of his drink. Mateo noticed that he was beginning to appear drunk, and he sighed in relief, knowing that he would not be questioned further.

“Oh, he was just... telling me about your conquest in the church.”

Tomás grinned and finished the rest of his drink. He almost fell over, and Mateo caught him in midair.

“I think I’ve had a little too much,” Tomás said, smiling brightly.

Mateo laughed slightly. “You should go to sleep.”

Tomás nodded in agreement, and Mateo walked him to his tent. Tomás threw himself onto the ground outside the tent's opening.

“Mateo,” Tomás said to the sky. “I don't care if you're keeping things from me.”

Mateo raised an eyebrow. “Really?”

“I think some things are better left unsaid.”

Mateo blinked. He went to protest, but when he looked over, Tomás was already asleep.

“Alright,” he whispered. “It'll stay unsaid.”

The grass remained silent in response.

CAPÍTULO 9

“Jacinto,” Solecito said exasperatedly. “Please don’t fight today. I’m going to stop by to drop off your lunch and you better still be there.”

“I will,” Jacinto said with a hint of annoyance.

“Jacinto. I mean it.”

“I will! I won’t fight.”

Solecito huffed and leaned down to fix his collar. “If you leave, I’m telling Mamá.”

“I’m more scared of you anyway.”

She sighed and pushed his hair out of his face. “If you say so.”

“Solecito... I’m sorry.”

“Sorry for what?” she asked, fixing his shirt absentmindedly.

“I’m sorry for everything I do that makes you upset.”

“You don’t upset me.”

“But I..”

“Jacinto, you’re going to be late.”

She pushed him toward the school gate, and Jacinto ran off to look for Fausto.

She sighed again and pulled on her braid. Even after he ran out of sight, she continued to stand still before the gate. Church bells were ringing in the distance, and she shivered. She pulled her shawl closer to her and proceeded to walk through the stones embedded in the road. She pressed her cross necklace closer to her chest.

When she arrived at home, Solecito immediately went to grab her bag of laundry and started walking down the road. Just like every other day, she carried her Roma powder and clothes to the river, where she began to soak and scrub her clothes.

To her right, she heard a sound, and she turned her head sharply.

“Solecito,” a voice called. “Please talk to me.”

Solecito’s blood froze. “Get away from me.”

“Solecito, please —”

“Don’t call me that.”

She moved back quickly to get away from him, but as she stepped back, she slipped. Before she could stop herself, she fell into the river, and it began to carry her away. Mateo ran forward and jumped into the water, rushing toward her. He grabbed onto her arm and began to pull her onto solid ground. Solecito coughed out the water in her mouth and began to cry.

Mateo embraced her, and she leaned on his shoulder.

“Please don’t hurt me,” she whispered. “I don’t want to be afraid of you.”

“I would never,” he said truthfully. He pulled her closer and squeezed his eyes shut.

“You saved me.”

“I did.”

“You saved me again.”

“I did.”

“Why?”

He paused. “I don’t... I don’t want to be like them. And I don’t want to hurt you.”

She sat back down on the ground, crossed her legs, and laid her skirt flat. “Why did you come?”

“I hoped you would be here.”

“But why?” She breathed shakily and wiped her tears.

“I’m not sure.”

Solecito breathed deeply. “I don’t know why I’m talking to you either.”

Mateo sat down, slowly. “So... someone told me that he saw me save you. In San Juan de Los Lagos.”

“Oh. I’m sorry. Is... something going to happen to you?”

“No. I think I can handle him.”

“Oh.” A long silence passed between them. “How did you know I would be here?”

“Wild guess.”

“*Why are you here?*” she pressed.

He shifted uncomfortably. “I want to do right by you.”

“Why?”

“Because you saved me.”

“And now you’ve saved me. We’re even. You owe me nothing.”

“That’s not true.”

“Why don’t you just go back to killing people? I know you enjoy it.”

He laughed despite himself. “And yet when I had the opportunity to kill everyone at San Juan de Los Lagos, I saved *you* instead.”

She scoffed and turned her head. “Just go away.”

“You said you don’t want to be afraid of me. So don’t be. Just *trust me*.”

Her lip quivered, and she eyed him carefully. She reached to place another shirt in the river, and he sprinkled Roma powder onto it for her. She began to scrub.

“How did you manage to come see me?”

“I brought my horse. They won’t notice we’re missing.” Solecito raised an eyebrow, and he laughed. “And if they do, I’ll handle it. There are too many of us to keep track of, anyway.”

“You said someone saw you save me.”

“He’s a special case.”

Solecito pulled the shirt out of the river and began to wring the water out of it.

“Do you think he followed you here?”

“No.”

Solecito paused, thinking deeply. She pressed the wet shirt against herself and smoothed it out with her fingers. The drops of water began to seep through her clothes.

“So... it’s *Mateo*.”

“Yes. I’m sorry. I didn’t want to scare you the first time we met, and I lied out of instinct. I had a feeling we... wouldn’t be on the same side.”

“Well,” she breathed. “Are we, *Mateo*?”

“Are we what?”

“On the same side?”

He folded his hands on his lap. “I’d like to think so.”

“All right.”

He watched her moving in silence as she went through the pile of laundry beside her. Her hands were beginning to dry from the soap, and the skin of her palms was beginning to crack.

“Can I make an observation?” She gave him a single sidelong glance, and he took it as a sign to continue. “You’re so serious.”

She scoffed. “We’re in the middle of a war.”

“That’s not what I mean.”

She frowned. “Then please, tell me what you mean.”

He wrinkled his nose slightly at the hint of sarcasm in her voice. “I mean, I don’t know. You’re so young. You’re practically still a child. And yet you’re so preoccupied with—”

“I am *not* a child.”

“No, you most certainly are not.”

She huffed. “I have many responsibilities.”

“I do, too. But I thought—”

“I carry a heavy burden.” He pursed his lips in response, and she continued absentmindedly. “I would think you of all people would understand. The burden you carry is more painful than mine. I met you while you were actively trying to run away from it, in fact. And...”

“And?”

She stared into his eyes intensely. “You’re a child, too.”

He extended his legs and pressed his palms down on his thighs. “Something like that.”

“Just because you laugh more than I do, doesn’t mean you’re any less serious or burdened than I am.”

“You’re right,” he conceded. “But I just thought... that things would be easier on the other side.”

“The war is hard for everyone, Mateo. But it’s harder on those of us who want it to end.”

His gaze wandered into the distance. “Oh.”

“Mateo,” she called softly. “Why do you fight?”

“Because they’re all I have,” he responded. “Why... why do you resist?”

“Because God is all we have.”

He nodded quietly. “I should go back.”

“I should too.”

Their eyes locked for a single, fleeting moment.

“Can I still call you Solecito? Is that alright?”

Solecito gathered the clean clothes into a sack and threw the sack over her back. “Yes. You can call me Solecito. *Adios, Mateo.*”

“Goodbye, Solecito.”

He watched her disappear again, just as he had before, but instead of the previous feelings of regret and guilt, he only felt a sense of peace spreading from his chest to his fingertips. He waited to see if she would turn back, just as he had before. Just as she was about to melt into the horizon, she turned back to face him. His heart jumped, and he smiled in response.

CAPÍTULO 10

“Are you with the *Cristeros*?” Gutiérrez demanded. He had Señor Cura Emmanuel pinned against the wall in a chokehold while his men stood beside him, threatening any who got in their way.

“No,” he whispered hoarsely. “I have nothing to do with them.”

“Then why are you here?” Gutiérrez demanded in his ear.

“I’m fulfilling my duty,” Señor Cura Emmanuel choked. His face was beginning to turn purple, and he began to claw at Gutiérrez’s hands desperately. “Please, I never meant any harm.”

Gutiérrez sneered and released him. Señor Cura Emmanuel fell limply to the ground, clutching his throat in pain.

“Burn it,” Gutiérrez said, looking around maniacally.

“But... they’re not *Cristeros*. They’re just...” one man protested. The rest of the men looked at him with a mix of confusion, anger, and shame.

“I don’t care if they’re *Cristeros* or not. Burn it down to the ground! I want every single corner of this place to crumble.”

Sebastián stepped forward eagerly to help Gutiérrez start the fire, and the flames began to consume the walls quickly. Gutiérrez and his men retreated quickly, and Mateo looked at Señor Cura Emmanuel sadly before he left.

Señor Cura Emmanuel rose from the ground rapidly, still clutching his aching throat. “We have to escape!”

He began to help the people of Las Amarillas escape from the burning church, and many of them ran out screaming. People were beginning to cough from the smoke, and his throat was beginning to hurt more intensely. He looked around the church through the falling ashes, trying to make sure that no one was left. The church was completely empty except for a man and a woman, who were holding hands and standing near the altar.

“What are you waiting for?” he yelled, holding back a cough that was threatening to surface.
“Let’s go!”

He ran toward them, but they stepped closer to the altar and shook their heads. His stomach dropped, but he understood and nodded grimly. As he ran past the walls of the church, which were beginning to fall, he heard them calling loudly to the heavens.

“Viva Cristo Rey!”

At first, they received no response.

“Viva la Virgen de Guadalupe!”

Señor Cura Emmanuel made it outside, with the rest of the people that had escaped the burning church.

“Viva!” a man in the crowd responded bravely. The crowd looked at him in shock.

“Viva la Virgen de Guadalupe!” they repeated, this time joined by Señor Cura Emmanuel.

“Viva!”

“Viva San Agustín!”

“Viva!”

“Viva Cristo Rey!”

“Viva!”

“Viva Cristo Rey!”

“Viva!”

They were not able to finish the last chant. The church crumbled suddenly, and the burning wood fell on top of their bodies, crushing them. Señor Cura Emmanuel bowed his head.

“Viva Cristo Rey.” he finished.

The people began to join their trembling hands, and they held each other in solidarity.

In the distance, the men had finished mounting their horses. Mateo had watched the scene unfold in horror. Some of the men cheered as they rode off, while others rode in silence.

The people began to pray loudly, and Mateo could almost hear them during the ride back, even though he was too far to hear them speak.

The angels in the heavens wept in response.

CAPÍTULO 11

“Is there any way I could have the money in advance?” Solecito pleaded.

Doña Magdalena frowned. “You’d have to ask my husband. He’s the one who decides.”

“Please,” Solecito insisted. “Please, I’ll do whatever you need me to. I don’t even want all of it. We’ve just been struggling at home recently, and I could really use the money. Please, I have my mother and my brother to think about.”

Doña Magdalena sighed. “I’ll see what I can do.”

Solecito smiled weakly. “Thank you. Thank you so much. God bless you.”

She turned back to the tiles she was scrubbing and continued to clean them vigorously. Her knees were beginning to ache unbearably, but she comforted herself with the knowledge that her duties were almost done. Although her job often exhausted her, she would do anything to make sure Jacinto could someday live a better life than her.

Suddenly, a loud crashing sound was heard outside of the house. Solecito heard Doña Magdalena scream in horror, and she dropped her brush and ran outside.

Señor Cura Emmanuel was lying on the ground before them. His throat was beginning to bruise from being strangled by Santiago Gutiérrez, and his face was dark from the ashes. He was coughing and choking on the ground, and Doña Magdalena rushed to help him sit up. Solecito ran back to the kitchen for water and quickly pressed a cup to his quivering lips.

“What happened?” Doña Magdalena asked in a trembling voice.

“I got everyone to safety,” Señor Cura Emmanuel whispered hoarsely.

“From where?”

“Las Amarillas.” He leaned forward and wiped his mouth with the back of his hand. “The *federales*, they found us in Las Amarillas while I was trying to take confessions. They came looking for Cristeros. They burned our church down.”

Solecito’s stomach dropped. *Was Mateo there? Did he hurt anyone?* “Oh.”

“How could this be?” Doña Magdalena asked. Her breath was shaky, and she collapsed onto the floor in shock. “They’re growing closer and closer to us. We’re going to be next.”

Señor Cura Emmanuel nodded solemnly. “We can only hope that God will choose to spare us.”

Solecito stepped forward and helped Doña Magdalena stand from the ground.

“I hope he will.” Solecito said grimly.

She put her arm around Doña Magdalena, and the three stood in silence.

“There was a man and a woman,” Señor Cura Emmanuel said. “They sacrificed themselves. They supported the Cristeros. They praised God until the end. When the church fell, I ran to the closest place I could find. I’m sorry, Magdalena.”

Doña Magdalena fell to her knees and began to pray. The grass blew back and forth at their feet in response.

CAPÍTULO 12

The night wind bit his arms, and Mateo shivered. He approached the house slowly. The moonlight was bright that night, and he used it to his advantage to not lose his way as he approached the window.

Mateo waited until he was close enough to see the ends of her hair on her pillow, and then knelt to pick up a pebble from the ground. He threw it at her window, softly. The pebble made a gentle impact and then fell to the ground. He picked up another and repeated the process. Then another. And another. She sat up in bed abruptly, and he ran toward her.

“Solecito,” he whisper-yelled.

She pulled her quilts closer and gasped. “What are you doing here?”

“I didn’t mean to scare you. I’m sorry,” he grinned sheepishly.

She rolled her eyes and opened her window. “You *did* scare me. Get out of here, Mateo Cruz.”

“Let’s go for a walk.”

Her eyes widened. “At this hour? No.”

“Nothing will happen to you if I’m there.” he boasted.

She rolled her eyes again. “I just want to sleep.”

“You’ve slept enough.” he pressed. “Besides, we both need to be back before the sun rises. Let’s make the most out of it.”

She huffed, but she threw the quilts off herself and ran to meet him. She was still wearing her nightgown, but she threw a shawl over it. Before going outside, she pressed her ear against Jacinto's door to make sure he was sleeping soundly. She waited until she heard his soft snores, and then she stepped outside.

“What do you want, Mateo?”

He grinned triumphantly. “To take a walk.”

“Where?”

“The river. Anywhere.”

“Why the river?” she asked. She wiped the sleepiness out of her eyes.

“It's the only place I know. But we can go anywhere.”

They made their way to the river, and she sat down next to it. She removed her sandals and dipped her feet in the water. She shivered slightly, but then relaxed. Mateo dipped his hand in the water and shuddered.

“How can you stand it?” he asked.

“You get used to it. Living here. It gets cold a lot.”

“Oh. That sounds nice.”

“Mateo, why did you look for me? Why do you keep looking for me?”

“I wanted to see you. I like seeing you.”

She lowered her gaze and began to kick her feet softly in the water. “Oh.”

“Do you like seeing me?” She turned her head over her shoulder and raised an eyebrow. He stifled a laugh. “All right, all right. How is Jacinto?”

She sighed. “He keeps getting into fights, running away from school, and just being rebellious. It makes everything so much harder for me.”

“Why is that?”

“I don’t know. I don’t know what’s going on. I don’t know how to help him.” She paused and licked her lips. “But I suppose...it could be because he feels lonely.”

“What do you mean?”

“He hasn’t been the same since my father left. And my mother...was never the same after that, either. I’ve had to take care of him since then, practically on my own. I think it’s gotten to him.”

“He probably does feel lonely,” Mateo mused. “I did too. Before...you know.”

“I know.”

“My father left me, too. And my mother... well...”

“I’m sorry.”

“That’s why I...” He cleared his throat and wiped his nose briskly.

“I’m sorry. I understand.”

He nodded and looked up at the night sky. All around them, crickets were chirping loudly. The sun had not yet started to illuminate the heavens, and he could still count the stars. “But I don’t feel lonely anymore. I have a friend now. His name is Tomás. He’s been there for me since we were kids. I don’t know what I would’ve done without him. He made it all feel...bearable.”

“That must feel nice. I wish I had had somebody like that.”

“It is nice. I just wish I didn’t have to lie to him all the time about coming to see you.”

“Why wouldn’t you tell him? I thought he’s been your friend for a long time now.”

“He has been. But I don’t think he would understand. We were raised...well, I mean, we were trained to think a certain way. I don’t think he would be willing to let go of that.”

“That makes sense.”

Mateo paused. “When did you start believing in God?”

She laughed in surprise. “What?”

“I’m serious. When?”

Solecito shrugged. “It’s always been that way.”

“So... you believe because you’re supposed to?”

She shook her head. “Not exactly. I... I spoke with God once.”

“How does that work?”

Solecito folded her hands. “We spoke in a dream.”

“So, it wasn’t real.”

“Just because it was a dream, doesn’t mean it wasn’t real.”

He hummed in response and laid back onto the grass. He tilted his head until the grass was no longer poking his neck. “I wish I could believe.”

She frowned. “Aren’t you trying to end that?”

“No,” he replied. “It’s not by choice. And it’s not that.”

Solecito laid down on the grass beside him. “You’d have nowhere to go if you left them, right?”

“Right.”

Solecito pressed her hand to her chest, where a rosary was resting gently on her chest. She passed her hands over its beads slowly, and then slid it up past her neck and face.

“Here.” She placed it in his hands. “Take this.”

He looked at it in awe. It was made of a fine gold chain and pure white pearls, which were shining in the moonlight. “Solecito, I couldn’t.”

“Yes, you could. And you’re going to.”

He laughed and placed it around his neck. After staring at it for a long while, he tucked it neatly beneath his shirt. “Do you think your God could ever love someone like me? After what I’ve done?”

“Yes,” she responded confidently. “He loves us all and He has a plan for all of us.”

“But how could his plan for me be to harm others? To burn churches? To be surrounded by people who enjoy ending lives?”

She sighed lightly and turned to face him. In that moment, he could almost feel her brown eyes piercing his soul. “Because that’s not His plan for you, Mateo.”

He pressed his lips together. “I hope you’re right.”

As the sun began to rise and the water in the river began to grow warmer, he slowly sat up. “We should go before I get caught.”

He stood up and reached for Solecito’s hand to help her off the ground, and she used her other hand to get back onto her feet. As they began to walk back to her house, neither one let go of the other’s hand. Mateo turned his head to hide the smile that was forming on his face.

“Can I ask you something?”

“Yes, you can.”

“What’s your favorite kind of flower?”

She raised an eyebrow at him confusedly, and he shrugged. “Bougainvillea.”

He blinked. “What? What’s that?”

She laughed despite herself. “The little magenta flowers that grow on walls. In vines. With the tiny white flowers inside.”

He nodded in realization. “That’s an answer I haven’t heard before.”

She shrugged. "I love the colors. They're so bright and beautiful."

They approached her house, and she pulled him behind the trees outside her window out of sight.

"Solecito," he began with a smile. "When can I see you again?"

She paused in thought. "Well...it is the end of August. We have our *fiestas* soon. There's one tomorrow night. You should come."

He blinked. "You mean...in front of all those people? Won't they recognize me?"

She shook her head. "A lot of foreigners come during this time. All the people who have moved to other states and to the United States visit. No one will be suspicious."

He began to grin. "Are you sure?"

"If you're willing to risk it, I am, too."

He nodded happily. "I am."

"The *fiestas* are always fun. And I think it'll be nice for you to see how my people express their faith. The fiestas are for San Agustín."

"All right. I'll see you tomorrow, then."

"See you tomorrow." She squeezed his hand before releasing it, and he began to walk away.

"Mateo! Please be careful."

"I'm always careful," he smirked.

She laughed and watched him walk farther and farther away. Right before he disappeared, he turned back to face her. She gave him one last wave and smiled. He waved back in response.

CAPÍTULO 13

Solecito walked out of the confessional with a heavy feeling in her chest. Although she had wanted to, she had not been able to bring herself to talk about Mateo with Señor Cura Emmanuel. She had thought that talking about it would make her feel better, but when she went to admit it, her breath caught in her throat, and she felt violently ill.

“Are you alright, my child?” he asked.

She realized she had been standing still outside the confessional for a long while. “Yes, I’m fine.”

He frowned. “What’s troubling you?”

“Just everything that’s been going on,” she answered, trying to convince herself that this was not entirely a lie. “I know they’re going to come for us eventually. And I’m not ready for it.”

Señor Cura Emmanuel nodded knowingly. “I feel the same way. But I have faith that God will protect us. Or, at least, He will make sure that things happen the way they are supposed to.”

Solecito shifted uncomfortably. “I have a question for you.” He nodded for her to continue, and she said, “Do you feel like you’ve ever done anything unforgivable?”

He furrowed his brow. “What made you ask such a question?”

She pressed her lips together. “I feel as though I deserve to go to hell sometimes.”

Señor Cura Emmanuel frowned. “What makes you say that?”

“I just... I don’t feel like a good person sometimes.”

Señor Cura Emmanuel placed his hand on her shoulder and led her to the altar. “Neither did he.”

Solecito followed his finger to San Agustín’s pedestal and looked at him in confusion.

“San Agustín was a drunk. He disrespected women. He disrespected his own mother. He was lost and misguided. He was a sinner, just like us, and still the Lord considered him worthy of becoming a saint. It is not always about the mistakes we make or the sins we commit. It is about our desire to change, become better, and seek His forgiveness. The Lord will never think badly of you, Soledad.”

Solecito nodded, and then another thought came to mind. “Señor Cura Emmanuel, are you afraid of dying?”

He seemed to be taken aback initially, but the moment quickly passed. “I am afraid of what they will do to us.”

“But are you afraid of dying?”

“I trust that the Lord will send me down the path I am meant for.” He shut his eyes and hung his head. “But...yes. I am afraid.”

“Why do you keep the church alive if it means that you might die?”

The priest hummed thoughtfully. “I could shut down the church to protect us all. At times, I’ve considered it.”

“Why don’t you?”

“My faith is greater than my fear.”

Solecito looked at him in awe. “You’re right. That’s how it should be.”

He exhaled deeply. “And there is no guarantee that they won’t come for us anyway, even if we try to do things their way.”

She nodded sadly. “What are we going to do when the day comes?”

“Pray.” he said simply. His expression was grim. “We must pray that the Lord will intervene. May San Agustín watch over us and protect us.”

Solecito bowed her head in response.

CAPÍTULO 14

The silence was sickening. Perhaps it was because she was afraid of being caught, but she felt as though her lungs had ceased to function.

Solecito stopped walking abruptly, and she felt pebbles cracking and sliding on the ground beneath her sandals. Her lips parted slightly to speak, but her tongue would not cooperate. The silence surrounding her was overwhelming. It was almost as though every stone, every stem, every stream, every ray of sunshine, and even the serpent himself were watching her, waiting for her to release the word that was pressing itself into the tip of her tongue. The word that was pushing and pulling against her throat, embedding itself into her skin, dissolving into her bloodstream, branding itself so deeply into the organ that was pounding ever so forcefully against her trembling chest that it would never be the same after this one fleeting moment. The word. The name.

“*Mateo.*” Barely above a whisper. A line of birds rose from the tree they had been resting on as soon as she said it, as if she had screamed it at the top of her lungs. She gasped as their chirps broke the silence and pulled her shawl closer.

“Solecito!”

She flinched and dug her fingernails into her shawl. “You scared me.”

“You came.”

“I almost didn’t,” she said dryly. “You know, you really should be more careful. I don’t want either of us to get caught.”

“Why? Are you embarrassed to be seen with me?”

She eyed him slowly and carefully, and her gaze lingered on his chest, which was hidden behind his uniform jacket. She looked at his jacket, buttoned with pristine, golden spheres. She looked at the shiny buckle of his leather belt, and at the way it sat comfortably against his waist, as if it were holding him in a gentle embrace. She stared at its dry, brown color until it screamed at her retinas. Her eyes dropped to the ground.

Solecito adjusted her shawl briskly, and her lips parted to respond. “Yes. And quite honestly, I should have *more* shame.”

Mateo smiled sheepishly. “I brought you something.”

She looked up quickly, forcing back the smile that was beginning to form on her face, and he placed a branch from a bougainvillea plant into her palm. The branch was freshly cut, and the flowers that were growing ever so sweetly on its surface were so vibrant that she could not take her eyes off of them. When she reached to touch one, it seemed to exhale softly in the passing breeze. A rush of warmth overwhelmed her senses.

“Bougainvillea. You remembered.”

“Can I put them in your hair?” he asked, gently.

She laughed softly and turned her back to him. He pulled the blossoms from their branch, one by one, and began to press them into her neat knot of dark hair. When he finished, he placed his right temple on her shoulder and sighed.

After a moment, she said, “I brought you some of my father’s clothes to wear. You’re not going to the festival wearing *that*.”

Mateo hid behind a group of trees while Solecito turned away, and he began to change his clothes. She bounced back and forth on her heels until he was finished.

“I buried my uniform under that tree over there, next to my horse.” Mateo said. Solecito turned back and saw that he was fixing the collar on her father’s shirt. “I’ll come back for it later tonight.”

Solecito felt her stomach twist into knots. Although she had been the one to offer him the clothes, she felt strange looking at him in her father’s clothes. However, the feeling dissolved when she noticed that he was wearing the rosary she had given him around his neck.

“We should start walking over. We’re going to be late,” she replied simply. As they started walking to the plaza where the festival would take place, she found herself holding back a smile.

When they arrived at the plaza, Mateo looked around in shock and wonder. The plaza was in the heart of Tlachichila, and its pavement transitioned smoothly into the stairs leading to the church. In the center of the plaza, a large kiosk was covered in banners and lights. To the left, a band was playing music, and vendors were selling tacos, tortas, sopas, and pozole. Milagritos had set up her stand, too, and she was selling corn and cut fruit. Jacinto was running toward her at full speed, wanting to buy his cup of fruit, and the sight made Solecito smile briefly.

“This is amazing,” Mateo breathed. “I never imagined it would look like this.”

Solecito shifted her weight from foot to foot. “There are usually more people here.”

“What do you mean?”

“It looks so empty.”

Mateo shook his head. “It looks so full of life to me. I’ve never seen anything like it.”

“Do you want to see the church?” Solecito asked cautiously. He nodded enthusiastically, and the two began to head up the stairs.

As soon as Mateo entered the church, he gasped. The place was overflowing with hundreds of flowers, and the ceiling was covered with white and gold silk banners. Mateo stepped closer to the altar, admiring the floors, columns, and the gold engravings on the walls. He ran his finger down the sides of the wooden pews and stepped forward before San Agustín, who seemed to be shining in the dim golden light. To his side, Mary and Joseph stood on pedestals, and the three watched him intently.

Mateo was mesmerized, staring into the eyes of San Agustín. He did not turn back until he heard a loud explosion outside. He gasped and ran back to the door. The night sky was illuminated with thousands of fireworks, all in different colors. They stepped forward and sat at the edge of the top stair to watch.

When the fireworks ended, they walked around the plaza, looking at all the stands and all the new people that had arrived. Solecito ran off to greet Milagritos, and Mateo stepped away. He came back holding two red, string bracelets, each with a silver charm in the center. Upon closer inspection, Solecito noticed that the charms had suns carved into them. Mateo placed one of the bracelets on her wrist and the other on his.

“There. So you don’t ever forget about me,” he said, grinning from ear to ear.

They took a walk around the plaza once more, admiring the way the lights illuminated the kiosk, and then they began to head back to her house. Solecito knew her mother would expect her to be home early, and she did not want to have to explain who she had gone to the festival with. When they arrived at her house, they hid behind the trees and talked for a while.

Finally, Solecito said, “Well, I should go inside. I have to make sure Jacinto doesn’t skip school tomorrow and I have to work, too.”

“I should go, too. I think I can manage to sneak back in unnoticed.” Mateo retrieved his clothes and dusted them off.

Solecito swallowed, and a feeling of dread filled her body. “Mateo...please be careful.”

He raised an eyebrow. “I’m always careful.”

She shifted her weight from foot to foot. “I know. But...be extra careful tonight. I don’t have a good feeling about this.”

“Solecito, don’t worry about me. Everything will be fine. This isn’t anything I haven’t done before.”

“Maybe we shouldn’t have done this. I have a really bad feeling about this. Please, promise me you’ll be careful.”

Mateo embraced her, gently. “I promise. I promise I’ll be careful. Please, don’t worry about me.”

“Alright. Goodnight, Mateo.”

“Goodnight, Solecito. I’ll come back soon.”

Mateo turned and left quickly. As he disappeared out of sight, Solecito lifted her head to the sky and began to pray silently. The stars blinked back in response.

CAPÍTULO 15

Mateo hid behind a tree next to where the soldiers had set up camp. He had been waiting there for hours, hoping that the soldiers would fall asleep sooner rather than later. His whole body felt frozen, his fingers were numb, and his breath was beginning to turn into misty clouds. Finally, when every soldier had been asleep for a satisfactory amount of time, he began to sneak into the camp carefully. He searched for Tomás's tent and moved toward him.

"You've done everything to make your excursions discreet, haven't you?" a voice called in the distance.

Mateo's head turned, rapidly. Santiago Gutiérrez was leaning against the trunk of a tree next to where Mateo had been hiding.

"I was peeing. In those trees." Mateo responded flatly.

"Is that what it was?" Gutiérrez asked, beginning to step closer.

"I don't know what you mean." Mateo said. He locked his jaw and tried to remain calm.

The two stepped toward each other until they were face to face. Mateo could practically feel Gutiérrez's breath.

"Where have you been?"

"I don't know what you mean."

Gutiérrez reached forward and, in a sudden movement, placed his hand around Mateo's throat. He began to apply pressure, and Mateo felt himself losing oxygen, but he refused to change his expression. Gutiérrez's eyes widened and he released Mateo. His fingers closed around the rosary on Mateo's neck, and Mateo's stomach dropped violently.

“Where did you get this?” Gutiérrez asked.

Mateo’s eyes began to fill with tears, but he fought them back angrily. “I found it during one of our attacks. I took it as a prize.”

Gutiérrez pushed his back into the trunk of a tree and Mateo groaned in pain. He reached for the rosary again and began to twist it around his neck until it was digging into his skin painfully.

“This can all end quickly,” Gutiérrez said. “Tell me the truth and I’ll let you go. *Where did you get this?*”

“Someone gave it to me,” he sputtered, clawing at his neck.

Gutiérrez pressed closer to him. He smelled of smoke and gunpowder, and the smell made Mateo feel even more ill. “Where have you been meeting that person?”

Mateo resisted, and his face began to turn purple ever so slightly as Gutiérrez applied more pressure against his throat. “If you don’t tell me, I’ll kill you.”

“You wouldn’t,” Mateo spat out. But as he began to feel more desperate for oxygen, he lost hope.

Gutiérrez released him and he began to cough violently. Just as he began to wonder if running would help him, Gutiérrez lifted a gun and pressed it against Mateo’s temple, in the same spot that had leaned against Solecito’s shoulder hours before.

“I’m only going to ask one more time,” Gutiérrez said menacingly. “Where have you been meeting them?”

Mateo’s legs gave out under him. “Tlachichila.”

Gutiérrez reached for the rosary around Mateo's neck and ripped it off. He threw it against the ground violently. Mateo watched him helplessly.

"I've been watching you all this time. I know you've been leaving."

Mateo lifted his head. "Why did you let me go?"

"You've always done everything right, Cruz. Since I met you. I never thought you would betray me this way."

"Sir, I wasn't trying to betray you. But I can't do this anymore."

"You owe me everything, Mateo Cruz. You would be nothing without me."

Mateo thought briefly of his childhood, in which his earliest memories were about learning how to kill. He thought of all the harm he had caused, and he thought about Gutiérrez, who had collected a group of lonely, little boys and made them into monsters.

"Well, then I guess I'd rather be nothing."

Gutiérrez stepped forward and punched his jaw. "I expected better from you. You are never going to escape me again."

Gutiérrez walked away, and Mateo crumbled. He began to cough and cry violently, and his whole body felt as though it were tearing itself apart. He began to search for the rosary in the grass beneath him, desperately.

In the distance, he saw one of the soldiers sitting outside a tent watching. He blinked away his tears and saw that it was Sebastián. Sebastián looked over at Mateo and began to laugh uncontrollably. Mateo buried his face in his knees in response.

CAPÍTULO 16

The ride to Tlachichila was one of the most silent rides they had ever had. The soldiers had all heard about Gutiérrez's confrontation with Mateo. Half of them felt pity, and the other half felt fear. Even the birds had disappeared from the skies that morning. Mateo looked over at Tomás, but Tomás was avoiding his gaze. At the front of the group, Sebastián was riding gleefully next to the general, and Mateo felt anger beginning to make his blood boil. He tightened his grip on the reins.

"Keep going, we're almost there!" Gutiérrez called in a booming voice.

Suddenly, Gutiérrez pulled back his reins, roughly. His horse neighed loudly, and he raised a hand for everyone to stop. Mateo looked up with a confused expression. The soldiers began to whisper amongst themselves.

Mateo craned his neck slowly and noticed that there was a beggar standing before Gutiérrez. The beggar was a young man, but his face was hidden by thick dark hair and a long beard. He had a pale complexion, and he was wearing frayed, white clothing. He was supporting his weight with a wooden staff.

"What do you want? Why have you gotten in our way?" Gutiérrez demanded.

"Please, do you have any food or water?" the beggar croaked.

"We have nothing for you," Gutiérrez spat. He tried to continue moving forward, but the beggar moved in front of his horse.

"Please, sir. I haven't eaten anything in days."

"That is none of my concern. Leave us."

“At least tell me where you’re headed,” the beggar pleaded. “Maybe I can come with you and find something to eat, there.”

“I will answer your question, but you will not come with us. We don’t associate with *beggars*.” The man nodded in agreement, and Gutiérrez smiled. “We’re going to Tlachichila.”

“Please don’t go there. Don’t hurt them. They’ve done nothing wrong.”

“I’ve answered your question. Now let us through.”

The man tried to protest, but Gutiérrez pulled on his reins again and continued down the path. The other soldiers trailed behind him with their gazes lowered. As Mateo followed them, he made eye contact with the beggar. His mouth suddenly became dry. The man looked familiar. There was something in his eyes that seemed to make Mateo’s head spin. His mind protested, but Mateo shook his head and tried to push the thought away. The beggar watched until he passed him completely. Mateo turned back one last time to look at him, but by the time he turned back the man was gone. Mateo rubbed his jaw in response.

CAPÍTULO 17

Señor Cura Emmanuel began a prayer, and the people bowed their heads. The church was silent that afternoon. The town had been filled with life and joy at the festival the night before, but now they had come back to reality. They had been waiting for the *federales* to attack their church, and they had been biding their time until the moment came, hoping their prayers would be enough to keep the soldiers away.

Solecito opened her eyes slightly and saw that Jacinto had rested his head on the edge of the pew before him. Her heart filled with sadness at the thought of how heavily the stress must be weighing on him.

Suddenly, the doors burst open. The silence was broken and replaced with screams as people fought their way to exit the church through the side door. However, the side door was quickly blocked off by more soldiers, leaving everyone else trapped inside. Solecito pulled Jacinto close to her and looked upon Santiago Gutiérrez's cruel face for the first time.

"Let them go!" Señor Cura Emmanuel. "Please, it's me you're after. Without me, they won't have anyone to lead their masses."

Santiago Gutiérrez dismounted his horse and began to walk toward him. The rest of the soldiers followed reluctantly, and people began to sneak out through the front door past the horses. Solecito pushed Jacinto to the door and felt a slight relief when she saw him begin to run down the stairs. Santiago Gutiérrez snapped his fingers, and his soldiers slammed the doors shut. Solecito's gaze moved away from the doors, and she found herself looking amongst the soldiers inside. She found Mateo's eyes. His lip trembled, and he mouthed the words, *I'm sorry*. She froze. He had been the one to lead them here.

"I should've known I would find you here." Gutiérrez began. "I should've known you would've tried to keep the church running."

“Please,” he pleaded again. “Let them go.”

Señor Cura Emmanuel opened his mouth to speak again, but before any words could come out, Gutiérrez shot him in the chest. He continued to shoot him, over and over, until Señor Cura Emmanuel fell to the ground. The shots echoed painfully in the church.

Nobody screamed. Nobody cried. Nobody fought back. Everyone remained silent, watching his body fall to the ground in shock. Mateo tried to run forward, but Tomás pulled him back by the shoulders.

Señor Cura Emmanuel looked up weakly. He stared into the eyes of San Agustín, sadly. “*Señor, cuídalos.*” He began to tremble, and his eyes began to close.

“Viva San Agustín!” he called proudly, using the rest of his strength.

He died with a single tear trailing down his cheek. Solecito’s lip began to tremble, but she took a breath to steady herself.

“Viva San Agustín!” she repeated.

At first, the people around her looked at her with fear, but little by little, they began to join.

“Viva San Agustín!”

“Viva San Agustín!”

“Viva San Agustín!”

Solecito stepped forward again. “Viva Señor Cura Emmanuel!”

“Viva!”

“Viva la Virgen de Guadalupe!”

“Viva!”

“Viva Cristo Rey!”

“Viva!”

“Viva Cristo Rey!”

“Viva!”

“Viva Cristo Rey!”

“Viva!”

Their last exclamation rang throughout the church, and the people began to come closer to each other. They looked straight into the eyes of Santiago Gutiérrez. They were not armed. They were not trained. They were not strong. They knew it was a fight that they would lose. But none of it mattered. They were ready to fight.

Gutiérrez stepped toward the altar. He pointed at the statue of San Agustín, and people began to run forward in protest. The soldiers held them back, and Tomás continued to watch Mateo to make sure he would not help them. Three of the soldiers stepped forward and began to try and lift San Agustín from his pedestal, but they were not successful.

“Try harder!” Gutiérrez called angrily.

But no matter what the soldiers tried, they could not lift him from his pedestal. Mateo watched the scene unfold and then looked back at San Agustín. He looked into his dark eyes and stared intently at his dark hair and dark beard.

“Tomás,” Mateo said suddenly. “That’s the beggar.”

“What?” Tomás asked.

“That’s the beggar. San Agustín. Look at him closely, Tomás. We ran into him on the road.”

Tomás scowled. “Shut up. I’m not going to believe your lies anymore.”

“Tomás, please. For the sake of our friendship, you have to believe me. He’s the beggar! He was warning us that this is a bad idea. We need to leave him and this town alone. We have to go.”

“We were never friends!” Tomás exclaimed, releasing Mateo from his grip and letting him fall to the ground. Mateo groaned in pain, but he stopped talking.

In front of them, Gutiérrez and his men had tried to set San Agustín on fire, but the flames did not engulf him and soon extinguished themselves. Gutiérrez looked around wildly.

“What’s going on? What are you doing?” He looked at all the people around him, but none of them offered a response. He began to point his gun at the crowd. “Answer me!”

“You won’t be able to defeat our faith,” a brave man called.

Gutiérrez aimed to shoot him, but the gun fell out of his hand. His hands began to shake. He looked toward the crowd, where many of the soldiers had fallen to the ground and were trembling violently.

“That’s the beggar!” Mateo yelled. “He warned us to leave this place alone.”

Tomás reached over and placed his hand over Mateo's mouth to silence him. Gutiérrez looked into San Agustín's face, and the sight terrified him. He called for his soldiers to retreat, and he began to run toward his horse as fast as he could. As the soldiers followed him, Tomás turned to look back at Mateo one last time. They shared a long look, and in that look, they remembered all the memories they had shared.

"I hope you realize you made the wrong choice," Tomás said.

Mateo looked around the church. He looked at the people holding each other, he looked at San Agustín standing on his pedestal, he looked at Señor Cura Emmanuel's closed eyes, he looked at Solecito, and then he looked back at Tomás.

"No. I made the right choice," Mateo said, finally.

Tomás's lip quivered. He turned away and followed the rest of the soldiers out, and Mateo knew in his heart that he would never see his friend again.

Mateo turned back to where Señor Cura Emmanuel was lying. Everyone had gathered around him, and they were beginning to sob. He looked for Solecito in the crowd. When she saw him, her gaze fell.

"Solecito, I didn't mean to. I didn't mean to lead them here. He – he caught me sneaking out and he attacked me and he...he broke the rosary you gave me. I'm so sorry. He knew the whole time."

Solecito began to shake. "So... all of this. It all happened because of us. We did this."

Mateo's heart dropped. "What?"

“If we hadn’t continued meeting up, then none of this would have happened. And Señor Cura Emmanuel would still be alive. This is our fault.”

“No. No, please don’t say that. We can fix this.”

Mateo tried to protest, but Solecito had already begun to remove the red bracelet from her wrist. She pressed it into the palm of his hand.

“No, we can’t, Mateo. We can’t fix this.”

Solecito turned to follow the people leaving the church holding Señor Cura Emmanuel’s body, and Mateo was left alone. He took off his jacket and let it fall to the ground, and then he stepped forward and knelt before San Agustín.

“I’m really sorry,” he whispered. “I never thought it would end like this. Please, please forgive me.”

San Agustín watched him silently in response.

CAPÍTULO 18

At the funeral, everyone was silent. Señor Cura Álvaro, who had known Señor Cura Emmanuel for most of his life, had come to bury him with the people of Tlachichila. Midway through the funeral, it had started to rain. No one had brought an umbrella. They stood there, feeling numb beneath the storm. When Señor Cura Emmanuel was buried, everyone stepped forward and set a white rose on his grave. Then, they all left, one by one, until only Solecito, Jacinto, and their mother were left.

“Can I have a moment to myself?” Solecito asked. “I just want to finish apologizing to him in private.”

Jacinto and her mother nodded, and they began to make their way home. Solecito knelt in the mud and began to cry.

“I’m so sorry, Señor Cura Emmanuel. I wish I could have prevented this. This is all my fault. I could have kept this from happening.”

“It’s not your fault, Solecito.”

Solecito looked over her shoulder briskly and saw Mateo standing over her.

“We could’ve stopped this.”

Mateo sat down beside her. “No, we couldn’t have. There was no stopping Gutiérrez. And even if it hadn’t been him, it could’ve been any of the other soldiers.”

Solecito lowered her head. “I just wish he was still here. I wish none of this had ever happened.”

“Me, too.”

The rain began to slow down, and Solecito dried her tears. “What are we supposed to do now?”

“What do you mean?”

“We had been waiting for them to attack for so long, and now they’ve attacked, and our priest is dead. What happens now?”

Mateo looked up at the heavens for a response, but none came. “You have to keep going to church.”

“What?”

“You’ll find a way. You have to keep believing that someday things will change.”

“And what if they don’t?”

“Solecito, I just saw your church get saved by San Agustín’s presence. I saw him when we were on our way here. He warned Gutiérrez. He was *here*. He was *real*. He’s real, and he’s watching over everyone in this town. You have to believe that things are going to get better.”

Solecito nodded. She looked up at the sky, where the sun was beginning to peek through the clouds. “And what about you?”

“What about me?”

“Are you going back to them? To Tomás?”

“No.” Mateo said firmly. “I’m never going back. But I have hope that someday Tomás will find me again, and we’ll be able to have the friendship we deserve.”

“And what will you do until then?”

“I don’t know,” Mateo admitted. He stood up from the ground and offered a hand to Solecito. “I think I want to just...learn how to live life properly. How to be a good person.”

“That sounds nice.”

“And you? What will you do?”

Solecito sighed. “Pray. Wait for things to improve. And make sure my brother doesn’t keep skipping school.”

Mateo and Solecito laughed, and they began to leave the cemetery. They walked down the road, and Señor Cura Emmanuel watched from above in response.

CAPÍTULO 19

The sun always remembered its place among the hills of Tlachichila.

It was just beginning to rise, and its rays were filling the heavens with tinges of orange, white, and purple. The air was crisp and filled with anticipation of the coming day. Everything was still. It had rained the night before, and the red earth was moist and bursting with the promise of what was to come. In the distance, a crowd of roosters began to crow, marking the inevitable start of the day. Soon, the town would come to life, as it did every morning.

As the rays of light stretched themselves onto the clock tower and lightly touched its surface, its bells began to ring over and over again, following the melody that had been ingrained in their cracks and crevices.

When the sun took its rightful place in the sky, the people of Tlachichila began to rise from within their clay homes, ready to take their own rightful places within the town. It was a new day, and everything had been calm.

The soldiers had not returned to Tlachichila. Tlachichila had a new priest, and he fought to keep the church running despite the circumstances. More people had gone back to church after they heard about San Agustín's appearance, and they truly believed that one day they would be able to worship freely again.

After all, they knew the sun would remember its place among the hills of Tlachichila, and each day would bring something new.

FIN.

Annotated Bibliography

Álvarez-Pimentel, Ricardo J. “Guerra fría, guerra cristera, guerreras católicas: El conservadurismo y feminismo católico de la Juventud Católica Femenina Mexicana (JCFM), 1926 - 1939.” *Nuevo Mundo, Mundos Nuevos*, 2017.
doi.org/10.4000/nuevomundo.71299.

- The article begins at the end of the war, explaining the compromises that were made to resolve it. Then, the article goes on to explain all the relevant events that led up to the climaxes of the war. The author then goes on to explain the evidence of feminism in Mexico during the war, as well as the role women played in supporting the forces and ending the war. This article is beneficial for my research because my protagonist is also a woman, so it will be useful to know and understand the roles that women played in the war.

Andes, Stephen J.C. et al. “Singing for Cristo Rey: Masculinity, Piety, and Dissent in Mexico’s Cristero Rebellion.” *Mexico in Verse: A History of Music, Rhyme, and Power*. University of Arizona Press, 2015, pp. 181-217.

- This chapter belongs to a larger piece of work, titled, *Mexico in Verse: A History of Music, Rhyme, and Power*, and it discusses some of the earlier stages of the Cristero Rebellion. The chapter describes how Pedro Quintanar took control of Huejuquilla el Alto, Jalisco, and then used it as a base to attack federal troops along with his fellow Cristeros. The chapter also describes *agraristas*, which were pro-government militias that were stationed in Valparaiso, Zacatecas (along with other locations). Although Quintanar earned many triumphs, he also faced many challenges due to the federal troops. The chapter is based primarily on the actions that occurred in Zacatecas, Jalisco, Nayarit, and

Durango. This chapter will be useful for my research because it will provide insight into how the Cristeros operated and fought back against the federal troops in Zacatecas.

Bailey, David C. *Viva Cristo Rey!: The Cristero Rebellion and the Church-State Conflict in Mexico*. University of Texas Press, 1974.

- The book covers the effects and events of the Cristero War, beginning in the early 1900s before the war began. In Chapter 4, the book details the decree signed by President Calles in 1914, which outlined the new laws regarding religion. In the next chapter, the author describes the beginnings of the rebellions, which started in 1927. Additionally, in 1927 the rebels that fought back were often disorganized and inexperienced, and the book explains the challenges that arose because of this. Finally, the book describes the role of the United States' government in the political aspects of the war. This book will be useful for my research because it will allow me to understand the political background and motives of the war.

Jrade, Ramón. "Inquiries into the Cristero Insurrection Against the Mexican Revolution." *Latin American Research Review*, vol. 20, no. 2, 1985, pp. 53-69.

- This article tackles the argument that the Cristero War occurred as a result of conflicts between the church and state in Mexico. The author argues that many of the published works discussing the war tend to pin the blame on one or many of the participating parties, and it seeks to analyze the reasoning behind this. The author also focuses more on Jalisco than all the areas involved in the war. The article concludes with the argument that the war was not solely motivated by religion; it was more primarily fueled by "sociostructural conditions and power conflicts." Although my novel is more focused on the religious motivations that fueled the war, this article is beneficial to my research

because it provides other reasonings and occurrences for the war, which fills in the gaps between all of the events leading up to the conflicts.

Meyer, John A. *The Cristero Rebellion: The Mexican People between Church and State, 1926 - 1929*. Cambridge University Press, 1976.

- In the third section, titled, “The Conflict Between Two Swords, 1925-1926,” the book details President Calles and his election campaign, along with his former opponent General Angel Flores, who was a descendant of the revolutionary family. Despite this, Flores was not supported by the church. The author also discusses Zuno, who initiated a persecution in 1924 and opposed Calles as a presidential candidate. He then enacted an attack against the church due to the political forces that were against him. Zuno’s actions played to both sides, but he was also opposed by both. This book will be useful for my research because it will help me to better understand the interests and intentions of both sides of the war.

Ruiz Scaperlanda, María de Lourdes. “The Cristero War and the Knights.” *Knights of Columbus*, 21 May 2020, <https://www.kofc.org/en/news-room/articles/cristero-war-and-the-knights.html>.

- The article describes the Knights of Columbus, who were in support of the Cristeros and defied the Mexican government. The article is divided into four sections: “Persecution Begins,” “An Organized Response,” “Leading the Charge,” and “Knights in Exile.” The first section covers the initial protests to the Calles Law, which eventually led to the Cristero War. The second section covers how the Knights remained socially and politically active, as well as how they were punished by the government for their actions. The third section covers the tension between President Calles and Pope Pius XI. Finally,

the last section covers the martyrs that were killed as a result of the war. This article will be helpful for my research because it allows me to consider other sources of rebellion during the war (other than the Cristeros). It also helps me understand many of the timelines better, especially the dates and events leading to the war before it began.

Wilkie, James W. "The Meaning of the Cristero Religious War Against the Mexican Revolution." *Journal of Church and State*, vol. 8, no. 2, 1966, pp. 213-33.

- The article is a research study intended to explore the original causes of the Cristero conflicts, their goals, and the aftereffects after a compromise was reached. The reason for this study was that the author noted that the Mexican government and church are often seen as a single entity although they were on opposite sides of the conflict. The study ultimately concludes that the Cristero War was unsuccessful, and a true compromise was not reached until 1937, at which point the church and state decided to make peace to combat the rising threats of communism and fascism. This article will be helpful for my research because it puts the origins of the war into perspective in a clear manner, and because it is parallel to the lack of a resolution that occurs at the end of my novel.